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Distribution, abundance and length of macrozooplankton species in Svalbard fjords

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Abstract**Faculty:** Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences**Degree programme:** Master's Programme in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology**Study track:** 2 years**Author:** Andreas Lunde**Title:** Distribution, abundance and length of macrozooplankton species in Svalbard fjords**Level:** Master's thesis**Month and year:** 05/2023**Number of pages:** 40**Keywords:** Svalbard, Macrozooplankton, Fjords, Amphipod, Krill, Arctic, Distribution, Abundance, Length distribution**Supervisors:** Associate Professor Jarno Vanhatalo & Professor Janne E. Søreide**Where deposited:** HELDA**Additional information:****Abstract:**

Macrozooplankton is an understudied size class of plankton in the Arctic, but even though species composition is similar around the Svalbard archipelago, the relative composition can act as a proxy for climate change. This study investigated if the fjords around Svalbard are similar in species composition and if any differences could be explained. 11 fjords were sampled with a focus on common and indicator species in terms of abundance, relative composition and length distribution. I found low presence of *T.libellula* and high abundances of *T.abysorum* and *T.inermis*. *T.abysorum* was the only species whose abundance was significantly correlated to water mass (Atlantic water), but *T.libellula*, *T.abysorum*, *T.inermis*, *T.longicaudata* and *A.digitale* all showed significant differences in length distribution. This study provides further understanding of species composition in the different high Arctic fjords around Svalbard.

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Introduction

Climate change is estimated to increase the temperature in the Arctic two times faster than the baseline for the rest of the world (Meredith et al., 2019). It can be seen in effect as the sea ice is disappearing (Meredith et al., 2019), glaciers are melting and the oceanic currents from the Atlantic are increasing in effect (Walczowski et al., 2012; Johannesen et al., 2012). Sea water density differ depending on its salinity and temperature, which makes it possible to trace the origin of the water masses in the highly interconnected Arctic Ocean which is particularly exposed to warm Atlantic Ocean currents in the European Arctic.

Fjord ecosystems can be used as model systems to study larger ocean ecosystems (Salvanes, 2001), such as the Arctic Ocean. Plankton are organisms that are unable to move against the ocean currents and they primarily reside in their preferred water mass, thus often acting as good water mass indicators (Søreide et al., 2003). As such plankton can act as proxies for climate change (Hays et al., 2005). Even small changes in environmental variables can amplify and become detectable among the plankton community (Taylor et al., 2002).

Macrozooplankton (10-40mm) is the large size class of zooplankton, which is an important size class as prey for sea birds like black legged kittiwake, *Rissa tridactyla*, (Vihtakari et al., 2018) or fish like polar cod, *Boreogadus saida* (Lønne & Gulliksen, 1989), and when occurring in swarms they become significant predictors for density of baleen whales (Ressler et al., 2015).

Svalbard fjord systems and surrounding ocean currents

Svalbard is an archipelago in the high Arctic between 76 and 81 degrees North. It lies on the Norwegian continental shelf with steep slopes into the deeper Fram Strait to the West and to the deep Arctic basin along the Northern Svalbard coast (Fig.1a). East and South of the Svalbard archipelago the Ocean is shallower, though there is a trench of deeper Ocean between Spitsbergen and Bjørnøya to the South. Warmer Atlantic water, named the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC), flows along the continental slope on the west coast of Spitsbergen (Fig.1b), bringing warm and saline water from the Atlantic establishing a boreal climate in what is considered a high Arctic location geographically. The North Atlantic current also enters Svalbard waters through a branch in the Barents sea affecting the climate in southern Storfjorden. Further North the current splits into one branch flowing northwards into the

Arctic basin and one branch flowing eastwards along the continental slope (Koläs & Fer, 2018) past Wijdefjorden and into the Hinlopen strait (Menze et al., 2019) and up along the northern coast of Nord-Austlandet. On the East coast of Spitsbergen, the influence is mainly brought from the Arctic Ocean (Fig.1b). Flowing Southwards, the East Spitsbergen current (ESC) brings Arctic water, which is colder and less saline than Atlantic water. The Eastern parts of Svalbard therefore have shallower oceans, the water is colder and contains less salt, all resulting in a habitat that has better conditions for creating sea ice. The ESC continues southwards along the east coast of Svalbard and eventually curves westwards around South Cape and flows northwards along the West coast of Spitsbergen. After the ESC curves around the South cape it is referred to as Spitsbergen Polar current (SPC). The general trend is that the Arctic water in the SPC is lighter than the Atlantic water in the WSC due to the salinity difference and is considered to limit inflow and effect of Atlantic water. The open deep fjords are more susceptible to inflow of Atlantic water as the entrance can lead Atlantic water from deep into the fjord as seen in Isfjordrenna outside isfjorden (Nilsen et al., 2008) and Kongsfjordrenna outside Kongsfjorden (F. Cottier et al., 2005). A strong inflow of Atlantic water can lead to changes in temperature and salinity, affecting the production of sea ice (Piechura & Walczowski, 2009).

The high latitude means there is strong seasonality in temperature and light availability as there is little to no light during the polar night (November-February) and constant daylight during the midnight sun (April-August). The extreme seasonality has led to a biological community adapted to take advantage of the productive spring and summer to survive the fall and winter. Seasonality also strongly affects the water in fjords. The fjord environment is very dependent on winter, and the sea ice conditions (Nilsen et al., 2008). During winter there is both thermal convection driven by cooling and haline convection driven by salinity changes (Cottier et al., 2010; Tverberg et al., 2019). The change in salinity comes by brine production as sea ice is formed (Skogseth et al., 2020). This brine is heavy enough to sink to the bottom of the fjord and mix the water. If enough ice is produced and enough brine is released it can mix the water column to a mostly homogenous water mass. During spring this homogeneity is starting to be lost as inflow from rivers (Killingtveit et al., 2003) and heating creates a warm and fresh upper layer, while the dense water from winter starts to be collected at the bottom of the fjord (Cottier et al., 2010; Tverberg et al., 2019). Summer is usually a three-layered

structure to the fjord consisting of a surface layer of local water (LW), usually significantly more fresh than deeper water masses (Cottier et al., 2010; Tverberg et al., 2019). Below is a layer of more saline and commonly intermediate water (IW) mass and at the bottom is winter cooled water (WCW) produced in the spring that acts as a cold and saline water mass cooling down the fjord. During autumn, thermal convection is equaling out the upper water masses, but since these months are not cold enough to form sea ice there is no haline convection to include the winter cooled water at the bottom of the fjord (Cottier et al., 2010; Tverberg et al., 2019).

Macrozooplankton in Svalbard

Around Svalbard most macrozooplankton species can be found ubiquitously. The relative abundance, however, can differ greatly between different locations based on the zoogeographical preference of each individual species, as found in the mesozooplankton community (Daase & Eiane, 2007). Krill, Amphipods, Arrow worms, Sea angels and jellyfish are among the most important groups of macrozooplankton in Svalbard waters.

Krill - Euphausiids

Thysanoessa inermis, *T.raschii* and *T.longicaudata* are *Thysanoessa* species of krill expected to be found around Svalbard. *Meganyctiphanes norvegica* and *Nematoscelis megalops* are larger euphausiids that can occur around Svalbard but are both considered more rare, especially *N.megalops* (Buchholz et al., 2010). All the krill species are considered to have their main spawning grounds further South than Svalbard, in the Barents sea and the Norwegian Sea (Dalpadado & Skjoldal, 1996; Orlova et al., 2015).

Amphipods - Amphipoda

Hyperiid amphipods are commonly observed in the pelagic in the Arctic. *Themisto libellula* (up to 45 mm) is the largest amphipod found in the Fram-Strait/Svalbard region (Koszteyn et al., 1995) and is considered to be an Arctic endemic species and a valid indicator of the presence of Arctic water (Søreide et al., 2003). The sibling species, *T.abysorum* is also common in Svalbard waters, but is considered to be a boreal species commonly found in Atlantic influenced regions (Dalpadado et al., 2001). *T. abysorum* is much smaller (max 18 mm) than *T.libellula* (Auel & Werner, 2003; Koszteyn et al., 1995).

Arrow worms - Chaetognatha

Arrow worms (Chaetognatha) are gelatinous predators commonly found in Svalbard waters. *Eukrohnia hamata* is a species often associated with bathypelagic and neritic habitats (Terazaki & Miller, 1982) and its presence in fjords could therefore be interpreted as a sign of recent inflow of water from outside the fjord. *Parasagitta elegans* is common in most fjords around Svalbard and is considered to be a more neritic species (Grigor et al., 2017).

Sea angel – *Clione limacina*

Clione limacina is an Arctic/ Arcto-boreal pteropod considered an indicator species for Arctic water around Svalbard (Søreide et al., 2003). It is a predator, primarily feeding on the smaller wing snail, *Limacina* spp. (Conover & Lalli, 1972). *C. limacina* can grow up to sizes of 70mm in Arctic waters (Lebour, 1931) and can store large quantities of lipids in case of little *Limacina* spp. prey for prolonged periods (Böer et al., 2005).

Jellyfish - Ctenophores and Cnidarians

Several jellyfish commonly occur in Svalbard waters, but the most common are *Beröe* spp., *Mertensia* spp. and *Aglantha digitale* (Jucker & Havermans, 2022; Lundberg et al., 2006; Majaneva & Majaneva, 2013; Walkusz et al., 2009). *A. digitale* is a hydrozoa considered of Atlantic origin, mainly preying on protists (Williams & Conway, 1981) and copepods (Pages et al., 1997). Both *Mertensia* spp. and *Beröe* spp. are predatory ctenophores, but *Mertensia* spp. is considered an Arctic species with higher lipid concentrations than *Beroe* spp. (Kohlbach et al., 2021; Lundberg et al., 2006). *Beröe* spp. is considered an Atlantic species more common in the southern parts of the Barents sea (Zelickman, 1972). *Periphylla periphylla* and *Cyanea capillata* are larger Atlantic jellyfish that have been observed to increase its range northwards in the Barents Sea as well as in Svalbard fjords (Geoffroy et al., 2018).

Previous studies

Between 1970 and 2009 there was an observed decrease of Arctic water in the Barents sea, simultaneously there was an increase in Atlantic and transformed water masses (Johannesen et al., 2012) confirming an ongoing Atlantification of the high latitude Oceans. Studies on prey composition in the Svalbard population of the planktivorous black legged kittiwake suggest there is a transition from Arctic species like *T. libellula* to more Atlantic species like the krill

species *T.inermis* (Vihtakari et al., 2018), indicating that the Arctic zooplankton community is changing. Studies on polar cod gut content have found a trend for the euphausiid to amphipod ratio to increasingly favor euphausiids since 1990 (Dalpadado et al., 2012). Dalpadado et al. (2016) found amphipods and euphausiids at higher abundances in Kongsfjorden compared to Rijpfjorden and Isfjorden. In Kongsfjorden the tendency was for *T.abysorum* and *T.longicaudata* to dominate the Atlantic water, while *T.inermis* and *T.libellula* were only found at higher abundances closer to the the colder glacial bay at the base of Kongsfjorden (Dalpadado et al., 2016), possibly suggesting the habitat for Arctic macrozooplankton is decreasing as Atlantic water and Atlantic species become abundant.

This study aims to expand geographically on Dalpadado et al. (2016) by including more fjords to improve our knowledge of macrozooplankton communities in Svalbard fjords. The following hypotheses were investigated:

H0. Macrozooplankton communities in Svalbard fjords are the same.

H1. Svalbard fjords have distinct macrozooplankton communities due to different physical and biological characteristics.

In total eleven fjords from all around the archipelago were investigated to compare the species composition and length distribution of macrozooplankton in fjords with distinct different physical environments deep versus shallow, and predominantly influenced by warmer Atlantic water versus colder Arctic water masses.

Materials and methods

Study locations

Isfjorden (ISK) is an open deep fjord containing mostly water masses of Atlantic origin. It is a large fjord on the west coast, branching off into several smaller fjords eastwards into Spitsbergen Island. The mouth of Isfjorden is about 12km across and the fjord reaches about 90km eastwards. There is no sill at the entrance to the main fjord, though many of the branching fjords have sill structures separating them from the main fjord water masses. There are also no glaciers terminating in the main body of Isfjorden, but there are several tidal glaciers in the smaller fjords connected to Isfjorden. At the deepest Isfjorden is about 400m deep at the mouth.

Billefjorden (BAB) is a deep sill fjord located at the end of Isfjorden. Due to the sill at the entrance and a tidal glacier, conditions in Billefjorden can produce winter cooled water similar to Arctic conditions, despite the surrounding Atlantic water masses. The fjord has an entrance of about 8km, reaches 30km inland and is about 190m at the deepest.

Kongsfjorden (KB3) is an open deep fjord on the West coast of Spitsbergen. It is further north than Isfjorden, but even though there are several tidal glaciers terminating in Kongsfjorden, it is considered to be mainly influenced by Atlantic water. At the deepest Kongsfjorden is 354m deep, the entrance is 11km wide and the fjord is about 30km long.

Wijdefjorden is a deep sill fjord on the Northern coast of Spitsbergen with a mouth 16km wide and the fjord reaches 100km southwards into a tidal glacier. Beyond the sill in Austfjorden this fjord is a sill fjord with Arctic conditions and seasonal sea ice. There are several tidal glaciers terminating in Wijdefjorden and the deepest point is found at 246m deep.

Rijpfjorden (R3) is a semi open fjord at the North coast of Nordaustlandet, with a mouth of about 50km wide and reaching 60km inland. There is no sill in Rijpfjorden, but the shallow shelf extending northwards severely restricts inflow of warmer modified Atlantic water. There are several tidal glaciers surrounding the fjord. At its deepest Rijpfjorden is 285m deep and is usually ice covered for long periods of the year.

Wahlenbergfjorden is an open deep fjord with the 11km wide mouth located in the Hinlopen strait and running for 47km rotated eastwards into Nordaustlandet. This fjord has several tidal glaciers, but the lack of sill means the water masses are influenced by surrounding water masses in the Hinlopen strait. At the deepest Wahlenbergfjorden is 254m deep.

Lomfjorden is an open deep fjord located on the western shore of the Hinlopen strait. Lomfjorden has a mouth of 9km and runs for 35km reaching a maximum depth of 211m though much of the fjord is around 110m deep. There is a tidal glacier terminating at the base of the fjord.

Southern Hinlopen (KP) is a strait between Spitsbergen and Nordaustlandet where the Arctic current runs along the eastern part and northwards while the Atlantic current runs from the west and southwards. The balance between the two currents can change the water mass

around Kiepertøya, an island at the southern mouth of the strait where the waters are about 110m deep. The Hinlopen strait contains several tidal glaciers and is usually at least partly covered in sea ice during winter.

Storfjorden is the largest fjord on Svalbard, covering the distance between Spitsbergen and the two south-eastern islands of Barentsøya and Edgeøya. Storfjorden is an open deep fjord, with a plateau in the northern parts. 176m is the deepest point, while the fjord is 160km wide at the entrance and 200km long. There are several tidal glaciers around Storfjorden and the fjord is usually covered in sea ice over winter.

Hornsund is an open deep fjord at the southern part of Spitsbergen. The mouth is about 10km wide and runs for 30km eastwards. The fjord is considered to be influenced by Atlantic water masses, even though there are several tidal glaciers and the fjord being 243m deep at the deepest.

Van Mijenfjorden (VMF5) is a shallow sill fjord on the west coast of Spitsbergen where there is an island blocking the entrance. Water can enter through two shallow straits (about 15m and 40m deep) north and south of the Island. At the mouth, Van Mijenfjorden is about 13km wide and runs for about 60km eastwards containing several tidal glaciers and reaching depths of 113m. The fjord is usually covered in sea ice during winter.

Figure.1. Location of Svalbard as compared to mainland Europe (a) and the fjord sampling locations(b). Sampling stations (labels and red dots, see table.1 for full fjord names) presented relative to each other and location within the fjords. Oceans depth (shades of blue) is indicated and water masses brought in by the East Spitsbergen current (Blue arrows) and West Spitsbergen current (red arrows) are visualized. Maps made with ggOceanMaps (Vihtakari, 2022).

Macrozooplankton sampling

Sampling was performed during two separate cruises. In September with R/V Helmer Hanssen (31.08.2022-10.09.2022) where macrozooplankton was sampled with larger a macrozooplankton net (Søreide et al. 2003) with a 2,01m in diameter with a 180 μ m mesh size using a fin to direct it. Hydrography and fluorescence were measured with a Seabird 911+ CTD with a fluorometer attached (Wenneck et al., 2008). During November, sampling was performed with R/V GO SARS – “Polar cod connectivity” with Nansen Legacy (Husson et al., 2023) (12.11.2022-19.11.2022). Sampling was performed using a krill trawl (Wenneck et al., 2008) with a 5m x 8m opening and a mesh size of 8mm. For time and locations see Table.1 and Fig.1b.

At each sampling station CTD measurements were performed first to avoid disturbing the water by other methods. The CTD was lowered and retrieved vertically while the ship was stationary. Sampling with the macrozooplankton net started at sampling station and continued in a circle around the station at an average speed of 2,5 to 3,5 knops. The net was dragged in a V-haul, starting at surface then descending to 10m above sea floor before

returning to surface. The krill trawl started at sampling station and then continued to trawl down to about 20m above sea floor. The krill trawl was hauled in a V-haul at an average speed between 2,5 and 3,5 knops for an estimated 45 minutes depending on depth conditions.

Most samples were processed on board directly following sampling. Processing started by removing by catch of large jellyfish like *C.capillata* and potential *P.periphylla*, but also smaller ctenophores as *Beroe* spp. and *Mertensia* spp. as these can dissolve and contaminate the samples when stored for longer. Samples were processed with the aim of identifying to species level at least 300 individuals morphologically under a stereomicroscope (Leica MZ12). Individuals too damaged to be determined to species level were identified to lowest possible taxonomic level. A plankton splitter (Winner & McMichael JR, 1997) was used to divide the sample by homogenizing the distribution then dividing it in two, thereby decreasing the number of individuals to a representative sub sample. From sub sampled stations one part was preserved in formalin and one part of a similar volume was frozen, if the catch was big enough.

After species identification individuals were length measured. The aim was to measure about 30 random individuals from each species. Where possible, individuals were laid flat and measured for total length from head to telson to the nearest millimeter, for krill this was done from rostrum to end of telson.

After individuals were length measured, they were sorted into plastic trays and dried overnight at 60 °C. Dried samples were stored in aluminum and weighed to the nearest milligram back in the laboratory at the University Centre in Svalbard.

Table.1 Sampling dates at each location.

Date	Time	Location	Fjord type	Depth (m)	Watermass	Latitude	Longitude
31.08.22	07:45	Billefjorden (BAB)	Deep sill	174	ArW	78.66	16.71
01.09.22	20:20	Kongsfjorden (KB3)	Open deep	290	AW	78.95	11.87
03.09.22	07:13	Wijdefjorden (WIJ)	Deep sill	207	AW	79.13	16.03
04.09.22	08:51	Rijpfjorden (R3)	Semi closed	250	ArW	80.23	22.26
04.09.22	15:50	Rijpfjorden (R3)	Semi closed	250	ArW	80.23	22.26
05.09.22	16:28	Wahlenbergfjorden (WaF)	Open deep	261	AW	79.63	19.77
05.09.22	22:40	Lomfjorden (LoF)	Open deep	92	AW	79.47	17.92
06.09.22	09:47	Hinlopen (Hin)	Open deep	110	ArW	78.94	21.94
07.09.22	08:21	Storfjorden (SF)	Open deep	169	ArW	77.49	19.16
07.09.22	19:00	Storfjorden (SF)	Open deep	169	ArW	77.49	19.16
08.09.22	18:43	Hornsund (HS)	Open deep	216	AW	76.98	15.74
09.09.22	16:01	Van Mijenfjorden (VMF5)	Shallow sill	95	ArW	77.77	15.04
10.09.22	06:07	Isfjorden (ISK)	Open deep	255	AW	78.32	15.16
12.11.22	12:44	Isfjorden (ISK)	Open deep	256	*	78.32	15.16
13.11.22	09:29	Billefjorden (BAB)	Deep sill	136	*	78.66	16.71
15.11.22	19:01	Kongsfjorden (KB3)	Open deep	353	*	78.95	11.87
17.11.22	08:53	Storfjorden (SF)	Open deep	179	*	77.49	19.16

Data preparation

From stations where subsampling was necessary, these subsamples were multiplied to an estimated total catch, then averaged between the subsamples for a final estimation of total catch abundance for the station.

The volume sampled was calculated based on Equation 1 below, where the measured distance is the output from a flowmeter (Hydro-bios, mechanical flow meter) attached to the macrozooplankton net.

$$\text{Sampled volume of water (m}^3\text{)} = \text{Measured distance(m)} \times \text{Net opening(m}^2\text{)} \times 0.3. \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

For the krill trawl data from flowmeter was not available so volume sampled was calculated by the trawl distance and speed (Eq.2) and the sample volume based on the trawl opening (Eq.3).

$$\text{Trawl distance (m)} = 1000 * \text{trawl distance (km)} = \text{Average speed} \left(\frac{\text{km}}{\text{h}} \right) \times \text{trawl time (h)} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$\text{Sampled volume of water (m}^3\text{)} = \text{Trawl opening (m}^2\text{)} * 2 * \sqrt{\frac{\text{Trawl distance (m)}^2}{2}} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

From total catch volume abundance * m^{-3} was then calculated by dividing the catch by the volume sampled. Relative composition was calculated by dividing total catch of individual species by total catch of all species.

Macrozooplankton taxa like krill and amphipods may portray swarming behavior (Tarling et al., 2009; Vinogradov, 2014), this is a tendency for a species to have a patchy distribution where density varies strongly within the habitat. This is particularly noticeable when sampling in a 3D environment, like a fjord. As a result, when sampling, depending on if that swarm is caught or not, estimations can provide a density different to the true abundance. Before performing statistical analyses on composition, the abundances were cube root transformed. This limits the effect of large or small catches, while avoiding issues of infinite logarithms.

CTD data on measured variables from R/V Helmer Hanssen September cruise was retrieved and analyzed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using packages oce, ocedata and dplyr (Kelley & Richards, 2022a, 2022b; Wickham et al., 2022). The salinity and temperature measurements were used to estimate water masses as defined by Skogseth et al., 2020). Based on the estimated water masses and plots of the relationship of temperature and salinity over depth (Appendix.1; Appendix.2) I estimated the representative salinity and temperature for the dominant water mass see Table.1.

Length measurements (total body length) were measured to identify potential population cohorts. I found two cohorts in *T.libellula*, *T.inermis*, *T.raschii* and *P.elegans*, and these were therefore divided into two length categories (Appendix.6). *T.libellula* that were caught in Hornsund were not length measured at the time and was later not found in preserved formalin samples. A population of *P.elegans* was found in Lomfjorden, but not length measured at the time and not found in formalin preserved samples later. Since length

distribution was not available for the relative composition of the cohorts in the *T.libellula* population in Hornsund and *P.elegans* in Lomfjorden was estimated based on an average relative composition from other fjords with the same water mass. Identification of cohorts from length distribution was performed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using packages tidyverse and readxl (Wickham et al., 2019; Wickham & Bryan, 2022), to structure the dataset and ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016) to plot histograms and look for cohorts.

Statistical analyses

Dominant water masses were used to estimate origin of the influencing water masses. I assumed local water, surface water, winter cooled water and Arctic water are all Arctic origin. This is assumed, because they are all produced as part of processes happening in an Arctic fjord environment because of brine production, meltwater runoff and Arctic water masses (Killingveit et al., 2003). Fjords dominated by Atlantic water or transformed Atlantic water are assumed to be influenced by Atlantic origin and classified as AW fjords. The assumption is that fjords containing Atlantic water were primarily influenced by inflow, while fjords containing Arctic water are influenced by local conditions or East Spitsbergen current. For further analysis, I divided the fjords into two categories: Arctic (ArW) and Atlantic (AW). Water masses were analyzed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using packages oce, ocedata and dplyr (Kelley & Richards, 2022a, 2022b; Wickham et al., 2022).

Principal component analysis (PCA) (Pearson, 1901) is a multivariate statistics tool that was used to find similarities between the macrozooplankton communities sampled during August and September. In this study the communities were sampling stations in Svalbard fjords . The PCA separates the correlations between abundances of macrozooplankton species into additive independent principal components (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016; Pearson, 1901). Using the principal components, I plotted my samples in a 2-dimensional plot (here using the two components explaining most of the variation) in order to visually present how close the different fjords are in species composition. Fjords that are closer to each other in the PCA plot will be more similar in species composition compared to fjords further away in the plot. The correlation between the variables (here species) and the principal components can be presented by a vector acting on the two presented principal components. The PCA was analyzed for eigenvalues and plotted using factoextra and ggplot2 (Kassambara &

Mundt, 2020; Wickham, 2016) in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt), the package readxl (Wickham & Bryan, 2022) was used to transfer the dataset into R-studio.

Redundancy analysis (RDA) is a method of superimposing a second dataset of samples and variables onto a dataset (Mcardle & Anderson, 2001; Steward & Love, 1968). In the case of this study this would be a dataset of environmental variables (Appendix.3) acting as measured variables from different samples, here the different fjords of Svalbard. This was then superimposed on the dataset containing the species abundances observed in different fjords, as considered in the PCA. This information will be presented as a percentage (constrained) explained by the external dataset and like PCA, the different variables in the external dataset will be presented in how strongly correlated they are to the given RDAs presented in the current plot. Using the RDA, I performed a selection process for the variables. This was done as a forward selection (Blanchet et al., 2008). When performing this I made an RDA with all explanatory variables and extracted the r^2 and p -value to be used as a baseline for creating a new model. I then perform a forward selection on the existing variables, considering what variable explains most of the variation observed. Once the best variable has been picked the model starts over again to find the next variable that is best suited to explain the observations. Here the model will compare the adjusted r^2 as adding another variable will inevitably cause the standard r^2 to increase, while adjusted r^2 will consider this and evaluate if the addition of a new variable is explaining enough to be worth the observed increase in r^2 (Blanchet et al., 2008). If the increased r^2 of the new model is deemed better than the null model, then the forward selection will continue until the best choice to achieve the highest r^2 is to add nothing or if the p -value of the new model increases above the p -value of the null model. The forward selection and RDA was performed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using packages vegan and adespatial (Guénard & Legendre, 2022; Oksanen et al., 2022).

To compare the similarities and dissimilarities of the sampling locations I performed an Analysis of similarities (ANOSIM) (Clarke & Green, 1988; Somerfield et al., 2021) and a Similarity percentage (SIMPER) (Clarke, 1993) tests on the different groupings. I divided the fjord stations into categories as Eastern or Western, Closed or Open and Arctic or Atlantic influenced. Closed fjords were considered all fjords with some restriction of inflow, including semi closed and sill fjords (Table.1). ANOSIM is a test for statistical difference

between two communities where the null hypothesis is that the two communities are the same. In this case, the two communities were the alternative categories. For comparing community samples, ANOSIM is better than ANOVA because it produces a dissimilarity index, does not assume normal distribution (Sommerfeld et al., 2021), and is applicable for skewed datasets. SIMPER is a statistical test for comparing similarity between sampling groups (Fig.1b; Table.1). This test will provide an output of percentage difference between groups and individual contribution of species responsible for the variation between the two groups (Clarke, 1993). ANOSIM and SIMPER was performed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using the package *vegan* (Wickham & Girlich, 2022), structuring the dataset for analysis was done using packages *tidyr*, *tibble* and *dplyr* (Müller & Wickham, 2022; Oksanen et al., 2022; Wickham et al., 2022).

Shannon's diversity index (Shannon, 1948) was used as a measure of the diversity in the Svalbard fjord communities. It considers both species diversity and relative abundance. Higher Shannon diversity index represents higher diversity, and a community with a Shannon index of 0 has 1 species. Analysis of Shannon's diversity index was performed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using the package *vegan* (Oksanen et al., 2022).

I used a Welch's *t*-test (Welch, 1938) to test if there was a significant difference between the Shannon diversity index of the Arctic and Atlantic influenced fjord communities. It was also used for the length distribution of the different species. Welch's *t*-test is a hypothesis test that has a null assumption that two groups have equal means (Welch, 1938), in this case the resulting *p*-value would be high if the species likely had the same mean length across different fjord types. Analysis and Welch's *t*-test was performed in R-studio (R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt)) using the base version of R-studio, packages *readxl*, *dplyr*, *tidyr* and *tidyverse* (Wickham et al., 2019, 2022; Wickham & Bryan, 2022; Wickham & Girlich, 2022) were used to structure the dataset.

Results

Water masses in fjords along the west- and east coast of Svalbard

Atlantic water was found to influence and dominate the fjords located along the West Spitsbergen, except for Billefjorden which was composed of Arctic (ArW) and Winter cooled water (WCW) (Fig.1.a). Isfjorden and Wijdefjorden (North Spitsbergen) contained a mixture

of water masses, but Atlantic water was prominent here (Fig.1a). The fjords along the east coast of Spitsbergen were characterized by colder Arctic water, except for Wahlenbergfjorden and Lomfjorden which were strongly influenced by transformed Atlantic water (Fig.1b). Rijpfjorden and Storfjorden contained primarily WCW and ArW, while southern Hinlopen (Kiepertøya;KP) was mainly influenced by ArW (Fig.1b).

Figure 2: Potential salinity (psu) and temperature (°C) in fjords along the (a) west- and (b) east coast of the Svalbard archipelago during August and September of 2022. Density is presented as curved grey lines. Points represent a single measurement in a fjord, indicated by an individual color, legend bottom left. Different water masses are defined as by Skogseth et al. (2020) represented in squares and labelled as SW=surface water, IW=intermediate water, AW=Atlantic water, TAW=Transformed Atlantic water, LW=local water, ArW=Arctic water and WCW= Winter cooled water. For full station names see Table.1 and for locations see Fig.1b.

Abundance in August and September

High abundance of macrozooplankton was found in Kongsfjorden (KB3), Lomfjorden, Hornsund, Billefjorden and Van Mijenfjorden, largely dominated by *T.abysorum* and *T.inermis* (Fig 3a ; Fig 3b). Notable high abundance of *E.hamata* in Hornsund. The high relative abundance of *T.abysorum* (77%, Appendix.5) coincided with the fjords dominated by Atlantic

water, but also the Arctic influenced Rijpfjorden (Fig. 3a;Fig.3b). *T.inermis* was found in high numbers and relative abundance (53%, Appendix.5) in Arctic influenced fjords (Fig.3a), in addition to the Atlantic influenced Kongsfjorden and Isfjorden (Fig.3b). *Mertensia* spp. was only found in Arctic water dominated fjords except for one individual in Isfjorden (IsK).

Figure 3: Macrozooplankton community composition in Svalbard fjords as (a) abundance $\times m^{-3}$ and (b) relative abundance in August- September 2022. Dominant water mass indicated as red station name for Atlantic origin and blue station name for Arctic origin.

Abundance in November

In the krill trawl the catches were strongly dominated by krill species in all fjords (mean = 89%). *T.inermis* was by far the most abundant, except in Isfjorden where also *M.norvegica* was found in high numbers (Fig 4.a;Fig.4.b). *T.libellula* was only found in Billefjorden and the

abundance was very low (Fig.4a;Fig.4b) and *T.abysorum* was mostly absent except for some individuals found in Billefjorden. Kongsfjorden had the highest abundance of macrozooplankton, dominated by the krill species *T.inermis* and *T.raschii*.

Figure 4: Krill trawl catch abundance of macrozooplankton in Svalbard fjords as (a) abundance x m^{-3} and (b) relative abundance from November 2022. Dominant water mass indicated as red station name for Atlantic origin and blue station name for Arctic origin.

Community composition and explanatory variables

PCA showed 44.3% of the observed variation in dimensions 1 and 2. This separates the groups of Arctic and Atlantic influenced fjords into overlapping ellipses (Fig.5a) of significant likelihood of being dominated by Arctic versus Atlantic/transformed Atlantic water. The ellipse of Arctic influenced water coincided with the krill species (*T.inermis*, *T.raschii* and *T.longicaudata*) in Billefjorden and Van Mijenfjorden and smaller individuals of *T.libellula* (<25mm) in Hinlopen (Fig.5a; Fig.5b). The ellipse of Atlantic influenced fjords coincided with *H.medusarum*, *E.flammea* and *C.limacina* in Wijdefjorden opposed to *E.hamata* and

T.abysorum in Lomfjorden and Kongsfjorden (Fig.5a ; Fig.5b). The distribution suggest Billefjorden and Van Mijenfjorden were similar, that there is a group of Lomfjorden, Kongsfjorden, Isfjorden, Wahlenbergfjorden, Hornsund, Rijpfjorden, Storfjorden and Hinlopen, and that Wijdefjorden was different.

Figure 5: Autumn macrozooplankton community in Svalbard fjords represented by distribution of fjords (a) and the 15 most influential species shown. Dominant water mass in the fjord is indicated by color and an ellipse providing 50% probability of including a fjord under that category.

Forward selection of environmental variables (Appendix.3) using adjusted r^2 found none of the explanatory variables to significantly explain the observed variation in species composition. For plot of RDA see Appendix.5.

Table 2: Explanatory power of environmental variables (adj. r^2) for observed variation of species composition and abundance in Svalbard fjords during August and September.

Variable	Adj. r^2
Temperature	0.035
Salinity	0.011
Fluorescence	0.009
<none>	0.000
Turbidity	-0.001
Density	-0.002
Oxygen	-0.034
Depth	-0.041

Location and fjord type was not found to significant explain variations in the macrozooplankton distribution patterns, but origin of dominant water mass was (Table.3). The R-value was low (0.31) suggesting there is overlap in variation between the groups and within the groups.

Table 3: Explanatory significance of categorical variables on observed variation of species composition and abundance in Svalbard fjords during August and September.

Categorical variable	Significance
Location (West-East)	0.399
Fjord type (Open-Restricted)	0.449
Watermass (AW,ArW)	0.019*

Atlantic influenced fjords in Svalbard was dominated by *T.abysorum*, while the average Arctic influenced fjord was dominated by krill, mainly *T. inermis* (Fig.6a; Appendix.5). *T. abysorum* was responsible for 22% of the difference in macrozooplankton community composition between Atlantic and Arctic fjords, while 12% was explained by *T.inermis* (Appendix.5), although only *T.abysorum* was found to be significant (p -value=0.041). Fjords with Arctic water dominance had a macrozooplankton community being 58,3% similar, while similarity within the fjords with water of Atlantic origin was 58,6% similar. Average dissimilarity in

macrozooplankton community composition between the fjords of different water masses (ArW vs AW) was 44,8% (SIMPER). Shannon diversity index indicated higher diversity in Arctic fjords (Fig. 6b), but the difference was insignificant (p -value = 0.291).

Figure 6: Macrozooplankton communities in Svalbard fjords a) relative composition in Atlantic (AW) and Arctic (ArW) influenced fjords and (b) Shannon diversity index of Atlantic (AW) and Arctic (ArW) influenced Svalbard fjords.

Length measurements of macrozooplankton

The difference in measured length was significant between Arctic and Atlantic water dominated fjords for *T.abysorum*, *T.libellula*, *T.inermis*, *T.longicaudata* and *A.digitale* (Fig 7). *T.abysorum*, *T.inermis*, *T.longicaudata* and *A.digitale* were found to be significantly larger in Atlantic water, while arctic species such as *T.libellula* was significantly larger in fjords dominated by Arctic water masses (Fig.7). For length distribution see Appendix.6.

Figure 7: Length (mm) of macrozooplankton species in Svalbard fjords grouped for August, September, and November, divided into Arctic water (ArW) or Atlantic water (AW). Note that the Y-axis varies between species. Significant p -value is represented by “***”.

Discussion

The macrozooplankton communities in Svalbard fjords were found to be distinctly different if comparing fjords with primarily Arctic versus Atlantic water influence. The sill fjords were characterized by colder AW/WCW/LW. Billefjorden and Van Mijenfjorden were similar in their macrozooplankton communities while the open more Atlantic influenced fjords Kongsfjorden, Isfjorden, Lomfjorden and Wahlenbergfjorden showed high similarity in macrozooplankton community composition. Wijdefjorden contained a mixed water mass and was more dissimilar in community composition compared to the other fjords. The origin of the water masses was found to be a significant categorical difference to explain species composition in the fjords, while environmental variables did not explain the observed composition. *T.inermis* was the most abundant species in fjords Influenced by Arctic water, while *T.abysorum* was the most abundant in Atlantic influenced fjords. *T.libellula* was not found in the high numbers expected, and was even absent from most fjord samples. There was not a significant difference in Shannon’s diversity index between the two categories of

Arctic and Atlantic water. *T.abysorum*, *T.inermis*, *T.longicaudata*, *T.libellula* and *A.digitale* showed a significant difference in length distribution in ArW versus AW dominated locations.

Differences in abundance and length between species across fjords

T.abysorum was the most abundant species in Atlantic influenced fjords. This corresponds to previous findings suggesting *T.abysorum* is the most abundant species in the more Atlantic influenced parts of Kongsfjorden (Dalpadado et al., 2016). *T.abysorum* was found to have a significant positive correlation to Atlantic water in terms of abundance and length, previously studies have not found a significant size correlation (Dalpadado et al., 2016). These results are interesting as they suggest *T.abysorum* might not be capable of establishing itself in the Arctic water masses around Svalbard. This could be explained by the low lipid content in *T.abysorum* compared to Arctic species (Nowicki et al., 2023), possibly resulting in it not being able to survive harsher Arctic conditions; resulting in the decreased size in Arctic fjords found in this study. In Rijpfjorden, however, *T.abysorum* was found to be the dominant species, even though that was dominated by Arctic water. Other studies have previously found *T.abysorum* to be abundant in Rijpfjorden (Dalpadado et al., 2016) supporting these findings. This study found warm surface water in Rijpfjorden, suggesting the *T.abysorum* population could be explained by an increasing WSC influence (Merchel & Walczowski, 2020; Walczowski et al., 2012).

The dominance of *T.inermis* in Arctic influenced fjords supports earlier findings of *T.inermis* being more numerous in colder water masses than Atlantic species like *T.longicaudata* and *T.abysorum* (Buchholz et al., 2010; Dalpadado et al., 2016). Within this study the correlation between *T.inermis* and Arctic water was however not found to be significant and individuals were found to be significantly larger in Atlantic water masses, indicating that the species is closer to ideal growth conditions in fjords under Atlantic influence. *T.inermis* has been found to contain more lipids than even Arctic species like *T.libellula* (Nowicki et al., 2023), this could mean *T.inermis* is the Atlantic species best adapted to establish itself further North. *T.raschii* was the first euphausiid confirmed to be capable of spawning in Svalbard fjords (Buchholz et al., 2012), but *T.inermis* is also a likely candidate for spawning in the Arctic if Atlantification continues. In this study *T.raschii* was found to not have a preference for water masses, suggesting it handles Arctic conditions, but rarely in large abundances. *T.inermis* has been proposed as an Arctic indicator (Buchholz et al., 2010) while other krill species like the more

boreal *T.longicaudata* are true indicators of climate change in the Arctic (Buchholz et al., 2010). *T.longicaudata* length measurements suggest a significant increase in growth in Atlantic fjords supporting the notion that this species thrive better in warmer Atlantic water. *T.inermis* has been found at higher abundance further into Svalbard fjords where the water is colder while *T.longicaudata* and *T.abysorum* is dominant in the more Atlantic waters of the fjord mouth (Buchholz et al., 2010; Dalpadado et al., 2016). In the Arctic water by the glacial bay; *T.libellula* is considered dominant (Dalpadado et al., 2016). This could suggest *T.inermis* is an intermediate species and not adapted to the true Arctic conditions *T.libellula* thrive in, while *T.longicaudata* and *T.abysorum* will be the dominant species if inflow of Atlantic water increases further.

T.libellula was only found in low abundances, and the krill trawl that should be selective towards larger species found a dominance of krill clearly indicating the *T.libellula* population in Svalbard fjords is small and not a result of undersampling. This supports previous findings of decreases in the *T.libellula* population since 1985 (Dalpadado et al., 2012), this correlates with an increased influence of the WSC (Merchel & Walczowski, 2020; Piechura & Walczowski, 2009) and a decrease in Arctic water in the Barents sea (Johannesen et al., 2012). Thus this study suggests the decline of *T.libellula* found in Polar cod and Black legged kittiwake diets (Dalpadado et al., 2012; Vihtakari et al., 2018) could be explained by the population in the fjords is decreasing.

The origin of the dominant water mass was found to be the best explanatory variable for the variation in species composition. This supports the use of plankton species as indicators of Arctic water, such as *T.libellula* (Søreide et al., 2003) and *T.longicaudata* for Atlantic water ((Buchholz et al., 2010). The abundance of *E.hamata* in Hornsund and *T.abysorum* suggests inflow events as these two species are considered open ocean species (Mumm et al., 1998; Terazaki & Miller, 1982). These two species were not found in high numbers in the sill fjords of Billefjorden, Van Mijenfjorden and Wijdefjorden. These fjords appear to be dissimilar to the others and excluding *T.inermis* the variation in species composition is mostly explained by *T.abysorum* and *E.hamata*.

A study by Siferd & Conover (1992) found cyclic population patterns in *Beroe cucumis* and *Mertenisa ovum* suggesting a possible predator-prey relation between the two species. This study found *Mertensia* spp. only in Arctic water and a single individual in Isfjorden. Meanwhile

Beroe spp. was not found to have a clear preference for any water mass. This study is therefore not able to conclude on the relationship between *Beroe* spp. and *Mertensia* spp., but the lack of *Mertensia* spp. in Atlantic water suggest this is a more Arctic species. *A. digitale* was found to have a significant positive correlation between body length and Atlantic water, suggesting larger individuals could be advected into fjords by inflow. The species is considered Atlantic (Williams & Conway, 1981) and found at particularly high abundances in Wijdefjorden, but was not found to be significantly more abundant in Atlantic water as it was also found common in relative abundance in Arctic influenced waters of Rjippfjorden and Hinlopen. *P. periphylla* was not found in this study, though others have found it at an increasing abundance in the high Arctic (Geoffroy et al., 2018). There were several fjords where *C. capillata* was found. *C. capillata* can have negative effects on Polar cod populations (Crawford, 2016) and *P. periphylla* have been found to have a negative effect on fish populations in fjords on mainland Norway (Fosså, 2012). Based on these results this study can not conclude on the abundance of large jellyfish.

T. inermis* and *T. abyssorum* are replacing *T. libellula

Given the abundance of krill, in particular *T. inermis*, in the fjords around Svalbard and the uncertainty on foraging behavior by the different krill species (Båmstedt & Karlson, 1998; Huenerlage et al., 2016), understanding their trophic roles could be important. If *T. inermis* is an omnivore with a preference for calanoid copepods it is a direct competitor for resources with the small *T. libellula* population found in this study. Krill could also be an indirect competitor with *T. libellula*, due to *T. libellula* preferring a diet of calanoid copepods (Dale et al., 2006). Studies have found a negative correlation between krill and calanoid copepods (Stige et al., 2018) where an increase in either taxa results in an increase of a planktivorous predator negatively effecting the other species. If the krill abundance in Arctic fjords is due to a replacement of *T. libellula* it could affect the community structure as a dominance by krill would result in a community dominated by herbivores instead of predators. As of now the importance of herbivorous mesozooplankton like *Calanus glacialis* and *C. hyperboreus* is significant (Visser et al., 2017). The introduction of high density of krill species in the Arctic could lead to macrozooplankton competing with mesozooplankton as the dominant herbivorous in the Arctic and decrease prey for *T. libellula*. Krill species are nearly all omnivorous, with different focus on herbivory ranging from the near predator *M. norvegica*

to the near herbivore *T. raschii* while *T. inermis* and *T. longicaudata* are considered somewhere in between (Båmstedt & Karlson, 1998). This means krill are possibly capable of foraging for prey during winter, being less dependent on the spring bloom than calanoid copepods. Krill, like in particular *T. inermis*, are considered rich in lipids, mainly wax esters (Falk-Petersen et al., 1981) and have been found more energy rich than amphipods (Nowicki et al., 2023). Based on the findings in this study, there is a dominance of krill in several Svalbard fjords, particularly among larger macrozooplankton suggesting an increased energy availability for higher trophic levels. This has been observed as seasonally migratory whale species around Svalbard have been expanding their range Northwards (Storrie et al., 2018), this is assumed to be due to the increased availability of krill species (Storrie et al., 2018).

As this study found *T. abyssorum* to be the most abundant species in Atlantic influenced fjords there is a possibility that the niche for *T. libellula* is replaced by the Atlantic relative, similar to what has been found in Kongsfjorden where *T. abyssorum* is more dominant in warmer parts (Dalpadado et al., 2016). This study found *T. libellula* to have two cohorts, this is supported by other studies on *T. libellula* during fall (Dalpadado, 2002). Cohort observations can indicate life cycle differences, and *T. abyssorum* was found to have one cohort, indicating it does not have a multi-year life cycle, supported by findings of 1 year life cycles in the Barents sea (Koszteyn et al., 1995). Koszteyn et al. (1995) found *T. libellula* to have a 2 year life cycle in the southern Barents sea, but spending 3 years to finish its life cycle in Polar water. A 2 year old *T. libellula* would be expected to be about 35mm, while a 3 year old could be 45mm (Kraft et al., 2012). This study only found *T. libellula* estimated to be 3 years old based on Kraft et al. (2012) in Rijpfjorden. Larger individuals are expected to contain more energy as there is a near linear pattern for length and dry weight (Auel & Werner, 2003), and a pattern for energy content to increase per gram dry weight in larger individuals (Nowicki et al., 2023). This could partly be explained or artificially enhanced by the brooding behavior by gravid female *T. libellula* (Percy & Fife, 1981). Carrying their eggs and thereby enhancing their own energy content as seen from a predators point of view. This potentially making *T. libellula* a particularly important food source given it is capable of reproducing year round (Dalpadado, 2002) and the Atlantic fjords dominated by *T. abyssorum* seem like a decrease in food quality for higher trophic levels. The different timing of spawning events changing from year round, with a focus on September-June in *T. libellula* to May/June as seen in *T. abyssorum* (Dalpadado,

2002) could affect timing of both prey availability and predation. There are also differences in distribution in the water column as *T.libellula* is considered to have its main habitat significantly closer to the surface than *T.abysorum* (Dalpadado et al., 2001). In the Atlantic fjords dominated by *T.abysorum* this could make foraging for amphipods more difficult for sea birds.

Auel et al. (2002) concluded *T.abysorum* has a preference for omnivores, meaning it is on a higher trophic level than *T.libellula* who prefer herbivorous *Calanus* spp. (Dale et al., 2006), this could explain why *T.abysorum* have been observed with higher contaminant levels than *T.inermis* and *T.libellula* (Pouch et al., 2022). Marine mammals of the Arctic who feed on macrozooplankton need blubber as insulation, but this is susceptible to accumulate environmental pollutants (Balmer et al., 2015; Villa et al., 2017). Should *T.abysorum* establish itself ahead of *T.libellula* that could increase biomagnification of environmental pollutants (Dietz et al., 2000) for top predators like seals and polar bears.

Concluding remarks

This study provides insight into the macrozooplankton community composition in Svalbard fjords. It confirms that the population of *T.libellula* is declining in Svalbard fjords, and that the population of *T.inermis* in Arctic influenced fjords and *T.abysorum* in Atlantic influenced fjords are increasing. The macrozooplankton community composition was depending on the origin of water mass with distinct differences in community composition found in Arctic versus Atlantic dominated fjords. The same species occurred more or less everywhere, but the relative abundance differed. The abundance of *T.abysorum* was the only one found to be significantly correlated to inflow of Atlantic water. Length of *T.libellula* was positively correlated to Arctic water conditions, while negatively correlated for *T.inermis*, *T.abysorum*, *T.longicaudata* and *A.digitale* which all were significantly larger in Atlantic influenced fjords. I therefore reject the H0-hypothesis and confirm the H1-hypothesis that Svalbard fjords are different, both in terms of species composition and species characteristics. I propose that these differences originate in the origin of dominant water mass as warm Atlantic or cold Arctic.

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Appendix

Appendix.1: Temperature (red) and salinity (green) measurements over depth in fjords along the western coast of Svalbard taken in August and September 2022.

Appendix.2: Temperature (red) and salinity (green) measurements over depth in fjords along the eastern coast of Svalbard taken in September 2022.

Appendix.3: Metadata of environmental variables gathered from CTD-measurements during August and September in Svalbard fjords.

Depth (m)		Temperature	Salinity	Fluorescence	Oxygen	Turbidity	Density
BAB	174	-0.1677232	34.81578	0.01384053	87.42517	10.118765	28.02038
KB3	290	2.8722600	35.03126	0.01236559	89.06999	5.318830	27.91339
WF	207	-1.1628750	34.78356	0.01224662	87.02214	13.454361	27.98010
R3	250	-1.1253050	34.67727	0.01320957	88.63231	2.321104	27.89432
WaF	261	1.3301040	34.67242	0.01296788	97.26067	5.213400	27.75543
LoF	92	3.2664670	34.55185	0.02498733	97.02712	16.869052	27.49742
Hin	110	1.4417400	34.25903	0.02699410	99.29380	7.150589	27.41415
SF	169	-1.2496760	35.03667	0.02085444	86.73474	5.456435	28.18395
HS	216	3.6032390	34.85249	0.01254317	88.47363	7.327366	27.71045
VMF5	95	4.8386660	32.76800	0.06466328	98.03572	18.816875	25.92302
ISK	255	1.8476860	34.76719	0.01241369	95.47643	3.793415	27.78784

Appendix.4: Autumn Macrozooplankton community in Svalbard fjords (black) and their correlation to different environmental variables (blue) and species (red).

Appendix.5: Species contribution (0-1) towards dissimilarity between Atlantic and Arctic influenced Svalbard fjords during August and September 2022. The 5 most influential species shown. Others include species only observed once during sampling in August and September.

Species	Avg. ArW	Avg. AW	Contribution	<i>p</i> -value
<i>T.abysorum</i>	0.167	0.767	0.221	0.041*
<i>T.inermis</i>	0.529	0.220	0.124	0.232
<i>E.hamata</i>	0.043	0.269	0.088	0.152
Others	0.179	0.308	0.086	0.131
<i>T.longicaudata</i>	0.328	0.216	0.070	0.360

Appendix.6: Length distribution (mm and abundance) of macrozooplankton species in Svalbard fjords during August, September and November.